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Research Article

**A NOVEL APPROACH FOR MUCOADHESIVE BUCCAL
FILM OF NARATRIPTAN**Vogoti Jhansilaxmi¹, Jyothi Muddagoni¹, B.Manogha², J.Neeraja², Sravani Singh²,
B.Sravani²¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, Sree Dattha Institute of Pharmacy,
Sheriguda (V), Ibrahimpatnam (M), Ranga Reddy, Telangana, India²Department of Pharmaceutics, Sree Dattha Institute of Pharmacy, Sagar Road, Sheriguda,
Ibrahimpatnam, Telangana, India**Abstract:**

The present investigation is concerned with the development of buccal mucoadhesive patches. Naratriptan is used for acute migraine attacks, which were designed to prolong the residence time and thus to improve the bioavailability of the drug and its half-life. Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose (HPMC) is one of the polymers which is having good mucoadhesive properties. Therefore, various formulations were developed by using release rate controlling and gel forming polymers like HPMC K and Ethyl cellulose by the solvent casting method. In addition to this, glycerol and DMSO were used as a plasticizer and permeation enhancer respectively. All the formulations had good physical appearance and physicochemical properties. From among all the developed formations, since formulation F2 retarded the drug release in a controlled manner for prolonged period of more than 6 h, gave satisfactory bioadhesion for maximum duration of 6 h and drug diffused up to the 80%, so it was selected as the best formulation. Swelling studies indicated significant water uptake and contributed in drug release. The most satisfactory formulation had showed no significant change in physicochemical properties, drug content, bio adhesion properties, in vitro diffusion pattern after storage at $30 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ (65% RH) and at $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ (75% RH) during stability studies for 3 months as per ICH guidelines. Thus, best formulation satisfied physicochemical parameters, in vitro bioadhesion strength, in vitro drug release and requirements for a buccal mucoadhesive drug delivery system.

Key words: Buccal delivery system, Naratriptan, polymers, solvent casting technique, Mucoadhesive patches, In-vitro release studies.

Corresponding author:**Vogoti Jhansilaxmi,**Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics,
Sree Dattha Institute of Pharmacy, Sheriguda (V),
Ibrahimpatnam (M), Ranga Reddy, Telangana, India

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1. INTRODUCTION:

The unique environment of the oral cavity offers its potential as a site for drug delivery. Because of the rich blood supply and direct access to systemic circulation, the oral mucosal route is suitable for drugs, which are susceptible to acid hydrolysis in the stomach or which are extensively metabolized in the liver (first pass effect).¹ These sites for delivery differ in both structure and composition as well as in degree of permeability and therefore, also vary in their ability to retain a delivery for a desired length of time.² Buccal route of drug delivery is a good alternative, amongst the various routes of drug delivery. Buccal drug delivery is most advantageous because it abundant blood supply in buccal mucosa, bypassing the hepatic first pass effect and accessibility.³ However, peroral administration of drugs has disadvantages such as hepatic first pass metabolism and enzymatic degradation within the GI tract, that prohibit oral administration of certain classes of drugs especially peptides and proteins.⁴ Consequently, other absorptive mucosae are considered as potential sites for drug administration. Oral cavity has been investigated for number of applications including the treatment of periodontal disease bacterial and fungal infection, aphthous and dental stomatitis⁵. Over the last two decades mucoadhesion has become of interest for its systemic delivery by retaining a formulation intimate contact with buccal cavity. The term bio adhesion has been used to define the attachment of a synthetic natural macromolecule to a biological tissue for an extended period of time. When a substrate is a mucosal system adheres and interacts primarily with the mucus layer, this phenomenon

being referred to as mucoadhesion.⁶ The present investigation is concerned with the development of the buccal mucoadhesive patches, Naratriptan is used for acute migraine attacks which were designed to prolong the residence time and thus to improve the bioavailability of the drug and its half-life.

2.1 MATERIALS

Naratriptan was collected as a gift sample from Hetero laboratories, Hyderabad, Synthetic polymers, super disintegrants and other excipients were purchased from AR chemicals.

2.2 METHODOLOGY

Formulation development

Buccal patches containing Naratriptan were prepared by the solvent casting evaporation technique. The drug Omeprazole was dissolved in methanol. Polymers HPMC, and Ethyl cellulose were taken in a boiling tube, to this add Naratriptan drug which was previously dissolved in methanol. About 30ml of solvent mixture of dichloromethane: methanol (1:1) was added and vortexed. Sufficient care was taken to prevent the formation of lumps. The boiling tube was set aside for 4 hours to allow the polymer to swell. PEG was taken as a plasticizer and added to the mixture and mixed well. It was set aside for 2 hours to exclude any entrapped air and was then transferred into a previously cleaned petri plate (40cm²), drying of patches was carried out in vacuum oven at room temperature. Dried patches were packed in aluminum foil and stored in a desiccator for further evaluation.

Table-1: Formulation table of Naratriptan

S. No	F.Code	Ingredients (mg)				
		Drug (mg)	HPMC	Ethyl cellulose	PEG	DMSO
1	F1	10	20	-	1ml	0.1ml
2	F2	10	40	-	1ml	0.1ml
3	F3	10	-	20	1ml	0.1ml
4	F4	10	-	40	1ml	0.1ml

FT-IR study⁷

Compatibility studies of Naratriptan and the disintegrants were carried out by using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR). Fourier transform infrared spectra of the samples were obtained in the range of 4000 to 450 cm⁻¹ using a FTIR by the KBr disc method

Characterization of Buccal formulation

Physico- chemical evaluation^{8,9,10}

Physical appearance:

All the formulated Naratriptan films were observed for color, clarity, flexibility, and smoothness.

Folding endurance:

Buccal patches folding endurance was estimated by frequently double over at the same place till it broke. The number of times the film could be folded at the same place without breaking is the folding endurance. This was restated on all the films for three times and the mean values plus standard deviation was calculated.

Thickness of the film:

The thickness of each film was measured by using screw gauze. Buccal patches thickness was estimated at various sites on each patch and the average thickness of the Buccal patch was capture as the thickness of the patch.

Weight uniformity:

The formulated Buccal patches are to be dried at 60°C for 6 hours before trial. A identify the area of 4.52 cm² of film is to be cut in different parts of the patch and weigh in digital balance. The average weight and standard deviation values are to be calculated from the individual weights.

Drug content :

The formulated Buccal patch were assayed for drug content in each case. patches from each formulation were assayed for content of drug. Each formulation was casted in triplicate and one patch from each was taken and assayed for content of drug. The Buccal films (4.52 cm²) were added to conical flask containing 100 ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8 contain 0.5% SLS. This was then stirred with magnetic bead at 400 rpm for 2 hrs. The contents were filtered and the filtrate was analyzed spectrophotometrically. Similarly a blank was prepared from Buccal films without drug.

Moisture absorption studies:

The buccal patches were weighed exactly and placed in a desiccators containing aluminium chloride to maintain 79.50% RH. After 3 days, the films were taken out and weighed. The percentage of moisture uptake was calculated using the following formula.

$$\text{Percentage moisture uptake} = \frac{\text{Final weight} - \text{Initial weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

Moisture loss studies:

Three patches were weighed separately and kept in a desiccator contains calcium chloride at 37°C for 24 hours. Then the last weight was noted when there was no further change in the weight of the patch. The percentage of moisture loss was calculated using the following formula.

$$\text{Percentage moisture loss} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Final weight}} \times 100$$

Swelling study.

Three buccal patch were weighed individually (W1) and placed separately in 3% agar gel plates and incubated at 37 ± 1°C. After every 15min time interval until 1 h, the patches were removed from the Petri dish and excess surface water was removed carefully with blotting paper. The swollen patch was then reweighed (W2) and the swelling index (SI) were calculated using the formula given in equation.

$$[\text{Swelling Index} = [(W2-W1) \div W1] \times 100,$$

Where W1 = initial weight of the patch
W2 = final weight of the patch

In vitro release study:

The release rate of the drug was determined by using Franz diffusion cell apparatus temperature maintained at 37 ± 0.5 °C and stirred at a rate of 200 rpm. Sink conditions was maintained all over the study. The vessel containing 10ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8 phosphate buffer solution. Aliquots of 1ml of samples were withdrawn at various time meanwhile and then analyzed using a UV Spectrophotometer at 224 nm against blank. % release rate of drug was determined using the following formula.

$$\text{Percentage drug release} = \frac{D_a}{D_t} \times 100$$

Where, D_t = Total amount of the drug in the film
D_a = The amount of drug released

Stability studies:

Optimized medicated buccal films were subjected to short term stability testing. The Buccal films were sealed in aluminium foils and kept in a humidity chamber maintained at 40 ± 2 °C and 75 ± 5% RH for 3 months as per ICH guidelines¹¹.

3.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Compatibility studies of drug and polymers:**

All these peaks have appeared in formulation and physical mixture, indicating no chemical interaction between Naratriptan and polymer. It also confirmed that the stability of drug during microencapsulation process.

Fig-1 FTIR Studies of Naratriptan

Fig-2 FTIR Studies of Physical mixture of drug and excipients

Physical appearance and surface texture of buccal patches:

These parameters were checked simply with visual inspection of patches and by feel or touch. The observation reveals that the patches are having smooth surface and they are elegant in appearance.

Weight uniformity of buccal patches:

The weight of the patches was determined using digital balance and the average weight of all patches

Thickness of buccal patches:

The thickness of the patches was measured using screw gauge and the average thickness of all patches.

Folding endurance of buccal patches:

The folding endurance gives the idea of flexible nature of patches. The folding endurance was measured manually, patches were folded repeatedly till it broke, and it was considered as the end point. The folding endurance was found optimum and the patches exhibited good physical and mechanical properties and the average folding endurance of all patches.

Drug content uniformity of buccal patches:

Naratriptan buccal patches prepared with various polymers were subjected to the valuation for uniform dispersion of drug throughout the patch. In each case three patches were used and the average drug content was calculated.

% moisture loss:

The moisture content in the buccal patches ranged from 8.75 to 8.96%. The moisture content in the formulations was found to be increased by increase in the concentration of polymers.

The moisture absorption in the buccal patches ranged from 9.92 to 10.52%.

Swelling index:

The swelling index in the buccal patches ranged from 14.58 to 15.98 %.

%moisture absorption:**Table -: 2 Physicochemical evaluation data of Naratriptan Buccal Patches**

F. code	F1	F2	F3	F4
Thickness (mm)	0.31	0.29	0.24	0.26
Weight variation (mg)	48.24	47.86	46.56	41.22
Drug content	89.79	98.85	91.25	96.18
Folding endurance	78	81	78	79
% moisture loss	8.86	8.75	8.7	8.65
%moisture absorption	10.25	10.21	9.82	10.22
Swelling index	15.97	15.75	14.59	15.26

Drug release studies**Table:- 3 *In vitro* release data of film F₁ to F₄**

Time (hrs.)	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	F ₄
0	0	0	0	0
1	26.70	25.89	26.50	25.55
2	48.18	45.23	44.50	47.59
3	69.75	68.35	67.65	66.55
4	76.89	70.34	71.98	75.32
5	88.86	86.77	85.32	80.28
6	92.44	95.56	90.02	89.23

Fig:- 3 *In vitro* drug release of (F1- F4) formulation

Stability studies:

Optimized formulations F2 was selected for accelerated stability studies as per ICH guidelines. The patches were observed for color, appearance and flexibility for a period of three months. The folding endurance, weight, drug content, % cumulative drug release of the formulation was found to be decreasing. This decrease may be attributed to the harsh environment (40°C) maintained during the studies.

Table-: 4 Stability studies of optimized formulations

S.NO	Time in days	Physical changes	Mean % drug release		
			Naratriptan		
			25°C/60%	30°C/75%	40°C/75%
1	01	No Change	95.56	95.56	95.56
2	30	No Change	94.45	94.12	93.97
3.	60	No Change	94.29	93.98	93.54
4.	90	No Change	93.89	93.56	93.18

4.SUMMARY & CONCLUSION:

From this study it was concluded that the buccal patches containing Naratriptan can be successfully prepared by using release rate controlling polymers. Hence these formulations of Naratriptan buccal patches with having good permeability. FTIR studies revealed that there is no incompatibility or interaction between Naratriptan and excipients. Formulated buccal films gives satisfactory film characteristics like physical appearance, surface texture, weight uniformity, thickness uniformity, folding endurance, surface pH, percentage swelling index, percentage moisture uptake, drug content uniformity, in-vitro drug release. The low values for standard deviation for average weight, thickness, surface pH, percentage swelling index, percentage moisture uptake, in vitro drug release and drug content indicated uniformity within the batches. Based on in vitro drug release, formulation F2 exhibited a drug release of 95.50% in 6 hours. The drug release could be retarded more than 6 hr with controlled release behavior. The prepared buccal patches were found to stable after performing stability testing for three month. Short term stability studies of optimized formulation as per ICH guidelines indicated that there is no significant change in physical appearance, drug content determination and in vitro drug release. So finally, it can be concluded that mucoadhesive buccal films of Naratriptan could provide sustained buccal delivery for prolonged period. A further clinical investigation has to be conducted to establish the safety and efficacy of the developed formulation.

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